

ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY OF SMALL-SCALE INDUSTRIAL ELECTRIC SOLAR SYSTEMS FOR SELLING TO THE GRID: AN EMPIRICAL REVIEW OF PERFORMANCE AT TASHKENT LATITUDE

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Introduction.

Uzbekistan's commitment to the development of renewable energy sources is firmly rooted in its legislative framework. The founding document is Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-539, adopted on May 21, 2019 "On The Use of Renewable Energy Sources." This law defines the fundamental provisions governing the development and use of renewable energy, clearly defining what constitutes renewable energy sources (RES) in Uzbek law. The Law is supported by Presidential Resolution No. PP-4422 of August 22, 2019 that introduces accelerated measures for the development of renewable energy sources. Further to the point, The Presidential Decree No. UP-5544 approves the "Innovative Development Strategy.", setting a clear goal of achieving 20% renewable energy in the national energy mix by 2025, with long-term targets until 2030. This strategic vision underscores the government's commitment to a sustainable energy future, and the target is already being fulfilled ahead of time: over the first 10 months of 2025, Uzbekistan's solar and wind power plants have generated 9 billion kilowatt-hours of electricity since the beginning of the year (that means that roughly 12% of energy generation is being contributed by wind and solar during this year so far¹). As of October 2025, monthly, 1 bln. kWh of energy generation originates from solar and wind in Uzbekistan.

The country currently has 12 solar photovoltaic and 5 wind power plants with a total capacity of 4,682 MW.

Their operation is already estimated to have saved 2.73 billion cubic meters of natural gas and prevented the emission of 4 million tons of harmful substances into the atmosphere since the beginning of the year².

Solar energy transforms the contribution of the smallholding sector to the energy grid, allowing physical entities to sell directly into the grid. During the first three quarters of this year, private solar power plant owners in Uzbekistan received revenue totaling 153.6 billion sum from the state budget, with the largest volume of financial revenues being recorded in the Khorezm region, where households that switched to renewable energy sources received 42.6 billion soms in revenues. This makes the region the undisputed leader in the utilization of budget funds allocated to support green energy. Significant sums were also allocated to the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the Bukhara region, where subsidies reached 22.4 billion and 15.3 billion

¹ <https://www.uzdaily.uz/ru/proizvodstvo-elektroenergii-v-uzbekistane-za-9-mesiatsev-2025-goda-vyroslo-na-38/>

²

sums, respectively. In the capital, Tashkent, solar panel owners received 10.7 billion soms.³ Presently, physical entities receive revenues of about 1000 sum for every kwt*h of solar energy sold to the grid, while legal entities are compensated at the rate of 720 soms. (including VAT). Some Tashkent installations, like the subject of this study, are compensated for the production to the grid at the rate of 1000 sum /kwt*h (including VAT). How efficient are solar investment projects in an economic feasibility sense for their initiators? We believe findings from our case study bearing on that can have resonant implications as the economics of solar projects is generally linearly additive?

Data and methodology

In our survey, we analyzed the performance of 3 rooftop energy solar projects over 2024 - October 2025 located in the central areas of Tashkent city in order to attempt to calibrate the outputs coming from RETScreen solar estimator⁴ and evaluate the efficiency of solar projects at the Tashkent/Guliston latitude. One rooftop project consisted of more than 300 2m x 1m panels, with the overall rated power output at 170 kwt, the other consisted of 36 panels with some 20 kwt of the overall rated output, and the third project consisted of some 100 panels with the rated output of 60 kwt. Each installation came equipped with its own inverter. The rated power output of each panel was thus 0,560 watts. The selling price of electricity generated to the grid over the period was at 900-1000 sum per kwt-h (gross of VAT). In total, the projects are capable of generating more than 280 000 kwt*h of electric energy annually, doing that at the marginal operating costs of some 60 mln. sum. p.a -- mostly on account of cleaning and cooling.

The methodology we employ relies on the investment project feasibility analysis performed in real terms based on the periodic annuities without growth and reporting EUAC, NPV and IRR metrics.

Findings

Below, we report our preliminary findings on the performance of the projects.

³ <https://upl.uz/economy/57474-news.html>

⁴ <https://retscreen.software.informer.com/4.0/>

2025:3,44	2025:3,55	
Efficient daily performance time at the full-rated capacity: 4,7 hrs/day -- July 1.2 hrs/day – January	Efficient daily performance time at the full-rated capacity: 5,1 hrs/day -- July 1.2 hrs/day – January	Efficient daily performance time at full-rated capacity: 4,8 hrs/day -- July 1.4 hrs/day – January
Project 1 – rated at 170 kwt	Project 2 – rated at 20 kwt	Project 3 -60 kwt

Fig. 1. Production output for Tashkent solar projects surveyed, in kwt-h by month in annual cycle 2024-2025

Data in Fig. 1 on total production output of the solar panels (in kwt*h) support the peak-to-trough ratios like the ones reported by RETScreen software for the Tashkent latitude (3.01). The daily performance equivalent of the panels at full capacity is around 5 hrs over the peak month (July). We estimate the total Equivalent uniform annual costs (EUAC) for the installations to be at 950 sum per kwt*h, assuming the real cash flow discount rate of 9% p.a. (or 19% p.a. nominal) and the service life for the installations of 30 years (while ignoring the decline in the output performance with time).

Therefore, we conclude that the financial economics of solar panel generation at the latitude of Tashkent is close to the zero-NPV point for commercial initiators of small-scale (roof-top) solar projects where most of the energy is meant to be sold to the grid, making installations just about feasible for their initiators, but without any undue expectations in terms of associated economic rents. In the light of that evidence, it can be concluded that the government revenue support amounts to a break-even point for such projects, whereas a more pro-active solar energy policy awaits.